

TREATMENT , DIAGNOSIS AND REMOVAL OF SPINAL TUMORS BY MICROSURGERY

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Annotation: *Dear Reader, This article provides information about spinal cord cancer, a dangerous disease that has its place in world medicine today. Causes of spinal tumors, Tumors and their description, symptoms of lumbosacral spinal tumors, as well as information on the diagnosis and treatment of this disease. You can get much-needed information about traditional and surgical methods used in treatment. This article also provides information on tinctures used in the treatment of cancer. You can learn about the stages of its preparation.*

Key Words: *Causes of spinal tumor tumors, symptoms, analgin , aspirin*

CAUSES OF SPINAL TUMOR TUMORS

At present, there are no specific causes for the formation of tumors in the human body.

But there are several factors that increase the risk of recurrence:

The presence of tumor formation in the family;

dangerous work runs; premium radiation background;

prolonged exposure to the sun.

All of these factors increase the risk of tumor spread. In addition, on the surface of the spinal tumor affected by the following processes: injury to the posterior column; chronic diseases of the spine. The early stages are called primary in the tumor process. Cancer cells have only begun to appear in the spine, but it is a mild early stage symptom of a back tumor growing. Cancer cells that appear in the spinal cord are easily carried throughout the body, as there is an excellent blood supply. The solution in the vessels, cancer cells break down metastases that form in bone tissue. Therefore, as the tumor grows, the spine is a dangerous tumor, the symptoms of which at this stage are already well expressed.

TUMORS AND THEIR DESCRIPTION ACTION

Tumors can be benign or cancerous.

Variety of spinal tumors:

skeletal system tumor;

bone tumors;
tumors of various origins;
metastatic tumors; invasive.

For good includes: Osteohodroma. Sponge bone, covered with cartilage. Boys are the most common during this growth. Osteoid osteoma. It is increasing when a dense bone source appears. It occurs from an early age, mainly in boys. Osteoblastoma, seal the bones. This is very rare in children and adolescents. Large cell tumor. It consists of multi-nucleated giant cells. It is mainly formed in women. Eosinophilic granuloma, loose connective tissue in bone movement and abnormal cell growth. In hemangiomas. It can happen at any age. These anomalously developed blood vessels. Make out the aneurysmal bone bladder, the

venous structure of the essence areas and the bone that grows externally. Can occur in young children. The main cancer of spinal tumors: Clasmocytoma is a mixture of cells that have lost signs that distinguish them from others. Chondrosarcoma. It grows slowly. It consists of cartilage. It is more common in older men. Osteosarcoma. The fast-growing and consists of neoplastic osteoids, which may contain fibro and chondrosarcomatous components. Hat's sarcoma, in young children. The origin is unknown. Chordoma. It develops into chord bases. These are metastatic tumors of the middle spinal cord that can occur at any age, but often after 30 years. As a rule, the spinal cord is affected by tumors of the following organs: kidneys; breast cancer; prostate; Metastatic thyroid gland Symptoms of the thoracic spine are also manifested by a small tumor. It significantly affects the activity of the heart, lungs and blood vessels. Possible failures in these systems.

SYMPTOMS OF LUMBOSACRAL DEAD BRAIN TUMORS

Tumors in this section of the posterior column can significantly affect pelvic organs and leg tenderness. The slightest suspicion of the development of the disease can not be ignored. The symptoms of the tumor lumbar spine are as follows: regular back pain; difficulty walking; menstrual cycle insufficiency in women: dysfunction of the urogenital system; Sensitivity in the lower legs decreased; uncontrolled urination and defecation; weakness in men. The symptoms of lumbar spine are sometimes very similar to the symptoms of sciatica, the roots of the spine are compressed when the tumor grows. Such events were observed: sharp pain in the hips or buttocks; The lower legs may have a bluish color, which is cold to the touch, as well as a decrease in sensitivity, accompanied by discoloration. This can lead to paralysis or complete absence of sensitivity of the legs, which is a very

serious effect, the symptoms of which are manifested in the lower back, if the tumor is located in the lumbar spine, those very .

DIAGNOSIS OF SPINE TUMOR TUMORS

First of all, the patient should be examined by a doctor. What symptoms can be determined by a specialist during the examination:

- limited mobility;
- scoliosis;
- impaired gait, - - movement;
- muscle atrophy,
- involuntary muscle contraction;
- the most tense point;
- New education;

the presence or absence of muscle spasm, lack of muscle sensitivity; Thorough physical examination if there was a suspicion of a metastatic process, if there is a suspicion of an intrauterine disorder. If there are symptoms of a malignant tumor of the spine, of course, it is declared. The method of palpation: to clarify the diagnosis of breast cancer thyroid rectum, prescribed laboratory tests for prostate cancer. This includes: total blood count: urine. The patient is then referred for an X - ray. If there are suggestions that the swelling will take place, it is necessary to refer the patient for a more thorough examination by an oncologist and a neurosurgeon. in order to improve the localization of production in the tumor process and determine its step mris. This research is the most informativemethod. It gives a layered picture not only of the tumor but also of changes in neighboring organs, the degree to which it has grown in blood vessels and other tissues. In order to determine the level of tumor activity using radio isotope Co. How it works: The patient is administered a special drug intravenously with a radioactive label. This tumor accumulates in the tissues. It then determines how to distribute the drug to the organs using a special gamma camera. To determine whether it is cancer, and to find its structure, a biopsy is used. To do this, use a special needle that is placed deep in the tumor, remove a small piece of tissue and then examined under a microscope.

Selected separately. Maybe a combination of several methods. Let's see how the U.S. different treatment method.

1. Medicine. The use of drugs, analgesics, helps to cope with pain. This drug is used as an anti- inflammatory drug in the form of injections, injections - drugs and non-drugs.

These are non-narcotic drugs:

- "Analgin"
- "Diclofenac"
- „ Ketanov ”;
- " Nurofen ”;
- " Aspirin ”.

Drugs:

"Tramadol",

"Morphine"

"Promedol".

Drugs are only discharged for special reasons and special prescriptions are purchased. tumors

2. Removal of tumors is not always possible to give quickly, so it can be located very close to the spinal cord, the vital organs. How to remove the tumor How to remove the tumor completely;

The removed part of the existing part of the tumor. Surgery to relieve pain and reduce the appearance of other symptoms affected in other ways. In general, it does not affect the results. You can remove all or part of the tumor, but the metastasis remains. It reduces pain.

Treatment 3. Non- surgical method.

In such cases, if the elderly have a benign tumor of the spine, the symptoms are very mild or absent, because the method of observation is often chosen.

Chemotherapy is used to experience radiation or radiation to destroy the remnants of radiation from cancer cells or, if the tumor is inoperable or part of it, provided that the tumor does not grow and does not threaten other organs. This type of treatment can affect the number of metastases, which can not be removed, reducing the growth rate, reducing the size of the tumor. Targeted treatment. As a whole allows the use of drugs that cause minimal damage to the body, since the method is used in the treatment of strong toxic radiation therapy substances - radiation, it negatively affects not only the tumor process, the whole body.

TRADITIONAL TECHNIQUES OF TREATMENT

The treatment of brain tumors is worth saying a few words about traditional medicine. Use folk remedies for the treatment of diseases, ineffective in cable, which shows long-term practice. But the unrestricted use of these recipes good individuals. This treatment is prescribed by a doctor, do not leave. Start with some or national prescription you need only after consulting your doctor. Do not just rely on popular treatments, its use will be very small after the disease, its chances can be overcome. We say

some of the plants used in the treatment of spinal tumors alfalfa; jenshen; eman kema; Viburnum zubturum mummy; Saint loann wort and many others. To relieve pain prepare various liqueurs and charges. To reduce pain using a manuscript: It is necessary to take these components: cayenne pepper burning, paraffin, pistachio oil. Mix all the ingredients and wake it up for a week in a dark place, just rubbed before bedtime, Use tincture to prevent tumor growth. Here's the thing: It's made from ginseng root. It is necessary to grind and pour 0.5 liters of vodka, infuse in a dark place for three weeks. To apply 5 grams need 2 times a day. After 7 days, continue to take within a month, getting reduced to 2.5 grams per day. Then you have to take a break for 12 days and repeat the lesson again. It should be borne in mind that the presence of a tumor of the spine, it is not necessary to create a burden that is difficult to exercise. Care should be calm and follow a diet and give up bad habits.

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